

REVIEW: THE TREATMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE

**Ajay Koundal*, Pankaj Kumar, Sarita Sharma, Abhishek, Asso. Prof. Samriti Sharma,
Asso. Prof. Kavita Pathania**

Dreamz College of Pharmacy, Sunder Nagar, H.P.175036.

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***Corresponding Author**

Ajay Koundal

Dreamz College of Pharmacy, Sunder
Nagar, H.P.175036.

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ABSTRACT

The pharmaceutical industry plays an important role in improving human health and quality of life; however, it also contributes to environmental pollution through the release of pharmaceutical wastes into water and soil systems and these contaminants originate from different sources, including manufacturing processes, hospitals, households, and agricultural activities, and are often not completely removed by conventional wastewater treatment. As a result, they persist in the environment, causing risks to aquatic life, human health and the environment. Biological treatment has an effective, eco-friendly, and economical step for pharmaceutical and industrial wastewater management. In this method, microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, algae, and yeast are used to degrade organic pollutants into simpler and less harmful products like carbon

dioxide, water, biomass, and biogas under controlled conditions. The process is broadly classified into aerobic and anaerobic treatment, each suitable for different wastewater characteristics. Various techniques, including Activated Sludge Process, Sequential Batch Reactor, Trickling Filter, Membrane Bioreactor, Moving Bed Biofilm Reactor, and advanced anaerobic systems such as UASB and EGSB, are widely used for efficient pollutant removal. Despite certain limitations, biological treatment remains a sustainable solution for minimizing environmental and health impacts of pharmaceutical waste.

KEYWORDS: Pharmaceutical wastewater, biological treatment, physical treatment, chemical, treatment Pharmaceutical industrial waste, Environmental sustainability, Wastewater management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry has an impact on living being's lives because it is contributing to generating well-being in terms of health and quality of life for individuals, and it is one of the most relevant sectors for the economy at a global level. The Indian pharmaceutical industries are considered as the world's 3rd largest in terms of volume and 14th rank in terms of value. It is growing at about 8 to 9 percent annually and is estimated to be worth 4.5 billion dollars. The pharmaceutical industry is responsible for researching, developing, formulating, producing, and marketing pharmaceutical drugs, vaccines, and treatments for common and rare diseases.^[1] They play an integral role in disease management, control, and prevention, significantly improving the quality of life. The pharmaceutical compounds play an important role in the treatment and prevention of diseases in humans.^[2] But pharmaceutical residues may have undesirable or unwanted effects although the side effects of drugs on humans and the environment.^[3] Different industries including pharmaceuticals, chemicals etc. are speedily growing in India which disposes off their effluents into the streams either directly or after partial treatment.^[4] Over the years, pharmaceuticals such as diclofenac and ibuprofen in trace amounts have been detected in public water systems, groundwater and surface water. Unwanted medicines should be safely disposed of at a reduced financial cost to mitigate the public and environmental health risks. Lack of general knowledge of how to dispose of unused pharmaceuticals leads to improper disposal resulting in accidental toxicity, rising healthcare costs, landfills pilfering/scavenging, water supply pollution, anti-microbial resistance, and death. To mitigate such effects, pharmacists should raise public awareness about safe disposal practices.^[5] Pharmaceutical emerging pollutants (EPs), especially antibiotics, steroids, and hormones in aquatic environments, have become a global environmental issue as they are found to be toxic, persistent, and non-biodegradable, which pose significant risks to aquatic life and human health.^[6]

2. Sources of Pharmaceutical Waste

The pharmaceutical waste originates from different sources within the healthcare and pharmaceutical sectors. Pharmaceutical wastes arise mainly from manufacturing, human and animal excretion, and improper disposal of medicines and these things are released into the environment in active forms and may not be fully removed by wastewater treatment. This led to persistent contamination of water and soil.^[7]

2.1. Pharmaceutical manufacturing

Pharmaceutical manufacturing is a major point source of environmental contamination because of large-scale production of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). During production, residue of pharmaceutical compounds may be released into wastewater systems. If treatment processes are inadequate or inefficient, these contaminants can enter nearby water bodies, leading to cause pollution. These issues majorly observed in regions with a high number of pharmaceutical industries and this continuous discharge of residue results in increased pollutant levels in environment.^[8]

2.2. Human and animal excretion

A major source of pharmaceutical contamination arises from the excretion of unmetabolized drugs by the human and animals. It is estimated that 30–90% of orally administered pharmaceuticals are excreted as active substances via urine and faeces, contaminate water bodies, soil, and the environment.

2.3. Agriculture and veterinary applications

The antibiotic consumption in livestock is projected to increase by 67% by 2030 in developing countries. Excretion of unmetabolized drug residues of animals enters soil and water systems through manure application and agricultural runoff.^[9]

2.4. Aquaculture practices

The use of medicated feed in aquaculture leads to the direct release of pharmaceutical residues into aquatic environments through excretion and uneaten feed.^[10,11]

2.5. Landfills and waste management systems

Pharmaceutical waste disposed of in landfills may reach into soil, groundwater, and sewer systems, contributing to long-term environmental contamination.

2.6. Hospitals and healthcare facilities

Healthcare institutions contribute to pharmaceutical pollution through the disposal of medical waste, including IV fluids and syringes, expired medicines directly into sewage systems, thereby increasing pharmaceutical loads in wastewater.^[12]

2.7. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and municipal systems

WWTPs act as both receivers and secondary sources due to incomplete removal of pharmaceutical compounds. In some cases, only 9 out of 118 pharmaceuticals compound

were effectively removed despite high treatment efficiency, and approximately 13% of WWTPs showed elevated concentrations of drugs such as diclofenac and ibuprofen.^[9,13]

2.8. Households and improper disposal practices

Disposal of unused or expired medications through flushing or discarding in trash represents a significant source. Evidence indicates that these are the most common disposal methods at the household level, contributing to environmental contamination.^[14]

3. Types of Pharmaceutical Waste

Pharmaceutical Industries produces a lot of waste materials. Some of which are toxic for human health as well as the environment are also called non-biodegradable and some of which are less toxic or non-toxic called biodegradable waste.

3.1. Communal waste

Communal waste is also known as “General healthcare wastes”. It is a type of waste which does not contain any harmful chemicals, infectious material or any kind of radioactive compound

Example: Cardboard paper box, glass bottle, Food and vegetables waste etc.

3.2. Biomedical waste

Biomedical waste is also known as “Hazardous health care waste,” or “Special waste”. It is a type of waste which contains any harmful chemicals, infectious material or any kind of radioactive compound which is harmful for human health as well as the environment.

Biomedical waste further classifies as

- **Infectious waste:** These are those wastes which contain different types of disease-causing pathogens. It includes dressing, swabs, waste blood, tissue, culture, etc.
- **Anatomical waste:** It includes those infectious body parts and equipment which may be discarded after surgery. Example sharp blades, knife, sharps and spines etc.
- **Medical waste:** It includes expired or outdated medicinal waste which is not disposed properly.
- **Genotoxic waste:** It includes those pharmaceutical wastes which contain genotoxic chemicals or drugs mainly used in cancer therapy.
- **Chemical waste:** It includes those wastes of discarded chemicals which are used during laboratory experiments and expired chemicals, disinfectants, and medicines.

- **Heavy metal waste:** It includes waste of batteries, metal containers, aerosol cans, gas cylinders, etc.
- **Radioactive waste:** It includes leftover liquids from radiotherapy and waste from patients who were treated or tested using radioactive substances.^[23]

4. Impact of Pharmaceutical Wastes on Human Life and Environment

4.1. Pharmaceuticals in the Environment

Pharmaceuticals enter the environment through industrial pollutants, hospital wastes, and other pharmaceutical particles where wastewater treatment systems are often inefficient in removing these compounds completely. As a result, pharmaceutical residues accumulate in aquatic systems and may affect ecosystem stability by entering the food chain.^[15]

4.2. Toxicity due to Pharmaceutical Compounds

Pharmaceutical compounds can exhibit toxic effects even at low concentrations where up to 95% of certain antibiotics may be released unchanged into wastewater systems. Common drugs such as NSAIDs (e.g., ibuprofen, diclofenac) are frequently detected and associated with toxicity to aquatic organisms, human life, wildlife and environment.^[16,17,18]

4.3. Pharmaceuticals in Drinking Water

Pharmaceutical residues are detected in drinking water in low concentrations, typically in the range of nanograms per liter (ng/L). Various compounds, including antibiotics and analgesics, have been identified in water supplies. Long-term exposure may remain concerns for public health.^[19,20]

4.4. Health Risk of Pharmaceutical Effluents

Prolonged exposure to pharmaceutical wastes (residue) may cause adverse reactions and major health issues. Impacts include cellular damage, behavioral changes, and reproductive disorders. If exposure to hormone-based drugs, may lead to reduced fertility and population decline.^[21,22]

5. Pharmaceutical Waste Treatment and Disposal

Pharmaceutical wastes are managed by using multiple treatment and disposal methods to minimize environmental and health issues such as the following

- Physical Method

- Chemical Method
- Biological Method

5.1. Physical Method

5.1.1. Incineration

It is a method in which organic wastes are burned at high temperatures to convert them into ash, gases, and heat products. It helps reduce the volume of waste to about 20–30% of its actual size, and the process known as thermal treatment and used for solid, liquid, and gaseous waste, especially hazardous medical waste. However, incineration has some limitations like it may cause air pollution due to the release of harmful gases in environment and is not suitable for certain wastes like gas cylinders, reactive chemicals, halogenated plastics (e.g., PVC), and materials containing heavy metals like mercury or arsenic. Modern incinerators follow strict regulations and include advanced designs with pollution control systems (such as scrubbers). The waste produced must be disposed of in secure landfills. Although effective, incineration is expensive and requires skilled operators.^[24]

5.1.2. Autoclaving

It is used to kill the harmful microorganisms in biomedical waste by using steam under pressure. It works under specific temperature, pressure, and time conditions to ensure proper disinfection. This method may not be recommended for human anatomical, animal, chemical, or pharmaceutical waste. Before treatment, waste must be cut into smaller pieces, which may cause equipment issues. Then the treated waste can be safely disposed of in landfills, but the process also produces wastewater that may also be properly managed. Autoclave systems require trained personnel and involve moderate cost for operation and maintenance.

5.1.3. Microwaving

It uses electromagnetic energy to heat the moisture in biomedical waste, which helps to destroy harmful microorganisms. It shows efficiency when the radiation properly reaches the waste material. Before treatment, the waste must be shredded and moistened. This method is not suitable for human anatomical, animal, chemical, or pharmaceutical waste, and not for large metal items. After treatment, the waste can be safely disposed of in landfills. Microwaving uses less electricity and does not require steam, which is an advantage. However, it requires skilled operators, and shredding equipment may break down frequently. The overall cost is moderate.

5.1.4. Deep burial

It is used mainly in rural areas for disposing of human and animal waste. Waste is placed in deep pits, covered with lime, and then filled with soil. The site should be away from water sources and not prone to flooding to avoid contamination.

5.1.5. Secure landfilling

This method involves disposing of waste in specially designed landfills that prevent leakage and environmental pollution. It is commonly used for hazardous pharmaceutical waste, including discarded medicines and incineration ash.^[25]

5.1.6. Advanced immobilization techniques: Encapsulation and inertization

Encapsulation involves sealing pharmaceutical waste in containers filled with cement or similar materials, while **Inertization** mixes waste with cement, lime, and water to form a stable, non-reactive mass. Additionally, **Sewer disposal** may be used for small quantities of diluted liquid pharmaceutical waste under controlled conditions. Collectively, these methods ensure the safe handling, treatment, and disposal of pharmaceutical waste, thereby protecting public health and the environment.^[24]

5.2. Chemical Method

5.2.1. Ozonation (O₃)

It is a modern oxidation process (AOP) that utilizes ozone (O₃), which is a powerful oxidizing agent, for the treatment of industrial wastewater. It is widely used for treating coking wastewater containing complex organic pollutants such as phenols, cyanides, and dyes. Ozone reacts directly with contaminants or indirectly by decomposing to form highly reactive hydroxyl radicals (OH), that will enhance pollutant degradation. Ozonation is especially effective in removing color, odor, and non-biodegradable organic compounds, and it also improves the biodegradability of wastewater.^[26]

Procedure of Ozonation

- **Pre-treatment:** Wastewater is first subjected to processes like coagulation–flocculation or filtration then removes suspended solids that may hinder ozone transfer.^[27]

- **Ozone Generation:** Ozone is produced by using an ozone generator which is known as the corona discharge method, in which oxygen or air is used as the feed gas.
- **Ozone Injection:** Ozone gas is introduced into the wastewater through
 - a. Diffusers
 - b. Injectors
 - c. Bubble columns.
- **Oxidation Reaction:** It includes the breakdown of complex pollutants into simpler compounds Ozone reacts with pollutants by
 - a. Direct oxidation (O_3 reacts with organics)
 - b. Indirect oxidation (formation of OH radicals)^[28]
- **Contact Time:** Wastewater is retained in a contact tank for sufficient time which ensures maximum pollutant degradation
- **Off-Gas Destruction:** Unused ozone is treated using ozone destructors and prevents the release of harmful ozone into the atmosphere
- **Post-treatment:** Treated water may undergo biological treatment or filtration and removes remaining biodegradable products.

5.2.2. Catalytic Ozonation

Catalytic ozonation is a modern oxidation process (AOP) that enhances conventional ozonation by using catalysts such as metal oxides (e.g., MnO_2 , TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3) or activated carbon. The presence of a catalyst accelerates the decomposition of ozone into highly reactive hydroxyl radicals (OH), which significantly improves the degradation of refractory and toxic organic pollutants. This method is particularly effective for treating industrial wastewater, including coking wastewater from the iron and steel industry, as it increases oxidation efficiency, reduces treatment time and improves overall pollutant removal compared to simple Ozonation.^[27]

Procedure of Catalytic Ozonation

- **Pre-treatment (if required):** Wastewater is pretreated using coagulation (flocculation or filtration) process. This process removes suspended solids and improves process efficiency.
- **Ozone Generation:** Ozone is produced using an ozone generator (corona discharge method), where oxygen or air is used as the feed gas.

- **Catalyst Addition:** Catalyst like is Homogeneous catalyst (dissolved in water, e.g., metal ions) and Heterogeneous catalyst (solid materials like metal oxides or activated carbon) is introduced into the system.
- **Ozone Injection:** Ozone gas is bubbled into wastewater using diffusers or injectors. It ensures proper mixing with catalyst and pollutants.
- **Catalytic Oxidation Reaction:** Catalyst promotes decomposition of ozone into OH radicals. Pollutants are degraded through direct ozone oxidation and indirect radical oxidation (more powerful and faster)
- **Contact Time:** Wastewater is retained in a reactor for sufficient time which allows complete degradation of pollutants.
- **Separation (for heterogeneous catalyst):** Solid catalysts are removed by sedimentation or filtration. It can be reused for further cycles.
- **Post-treatment:** Treated water may undergo biological treatment or polishing steps. It improves final effluent quality.

5.2.3. Photolysis (UV Radiation)

Photolysis is an advanced oxidation process (AOP) that involves the use of ultraviolet (UV) radiation to directly degrade pollutants present in wastewater. In this process, UV light breaks down complex organic compounds into simpler and less harmful substances. Photolysis is particularly effective for treating contaminants such as phenols, dyes, and certain toxic organic compounds found in industrial wastewater, including coking wastewater. Although it can work independently, it is often combined with oxidants like hydrogen peroxide (UV/H₂O₂) to enhance the generation of hydroxyl radicals (OH) and improve treatment efficiency.^[29]

Procedure of Photolysis

- **Pre-treatment (if required):** Removal of suspended solids through filtration or coagulation ensures better penetration of UV light.
- **UV Light Source Setup:** Wastewater is passed through a reactor equipped with UV lamps having wave length 200–280 nm (UV-C range).
- **Exposure to UV Radiation:** Pollutants absorb UV light energy and chemical bonds in contaminants break down. This process is known as photo degradation.

- **Optional Oxidant Addition (Enhanced Photolysis):** Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) may be added, then UV light decomposes H_2O_2 to produce $\bullet OH$ radicals. It increases oxidation efficiency.^[30]
- **Reaction and Degradation:** In this process complex organic pollutants are converted into simpler compounds to reduce toxicity and pollutant load.
- **Contact Time:** Wastewater is retained in the UV reactor for sufficient exposure to ensures maximum degradation.
- **Post-treatment:** Treated water may undergo biological treatment or filtration to removes remaining biodegradable by-products.

5.3. Biological Treatment Techniques

5.3.1. Membrane Bioreactor (MBR)

MBR combines biological degradation with membrane filtration for high-quality effluent.^[31]

Procedure

Wastewater → Bioreactor → Microbial degradation → Membrane filtration → High-quality treated water

Advantages

- Excellent effluent quality
- Compact system

Limitations

- Membrane fouling
- High cost

5.3.2. Rotating Biological Contactor (RBC)

RBC uses rotating discs partially submerged in wastewater for microbial growth.^[32]

Procedure

Rotating discs → Biofilm formation → Pollutant degradation → Sludge removal → Treated water

Advantages

- Low energy consumption

- Efficient oxygen transfer

Limitations

- Sensitive to shock loads
- Mechanical maintenance required

5.3.3. Anaerobic Digestion

Anaerobic digestion is the breakdown of organic matter in the absence of oxygen producing biogas.^[33]

Procedure

Wastewater → Anaerobic reactor → Microbial degradation → Biogas production → Effluent discharge

Advantages

- Energy generation
- Low sludge production

Limitations

- Slow process
- Temperature sensitive

5.4. Biodegradation of Pharmaceutical Drugs

5.4.1. Diclofenac^[34,35]

Microorganism: *Labrys portucalensis* F11

Mechanisms

- Hydroxylation
- Dechlorination
- Decarboxylation
- Dehydrogenation
- Methylation
- HCl elimination
- Sulfonation

5.4.2. Ibuprofen^[36]

Microorganisms: *Patulibacter medicamentivorans*, *Pseudoxanthomonas* sp. DIN-3

Mechanisms

- Hydroxylation
- Dehydrogenation
- Oxidation
- Loss of carboxyl group
- Loss of hydroxyl group

5.4.3. Naproxen^[37]

Microorganism: *Pseudoxanthomonas* sp. DIN-3

Mechanisms

- Hydroxylation
- Ester group cleavage
- Naphthalene ring breakdown
- Loss of hydroxyl group
- Loss of glucuronide group

5.4.4. Sulfamethoxazole^[38]

Microorganism: *Acinetobacter* species

Mechanisms:

- Hydroxylation
- Oxygenation

5.4.5. Chloramphenicol^[39]

Microorganism: *Trametes hirsuta* (laccase enzyme)

Mechanisms

- Oxidation
- Dehalogenation

5.4.6. Amoxicillin^[40]

Microorganism: *Bosea* species As-6

Mechanisms

- Hydroxylation

- Beta-ketoadipate pathway oxidation

5.4.7. Paracetamol (Pathway 1)^[41]

Microorganism: *Pseudomonas moorei* KB4

Mechanisms

- Acetate release
- Hydroquinone formation
- Hydroquinone cleavage

5.4.8. Paracetamol (Pathway 2)^[42]

Microorganism: *Bacillus drentensis* strain S1

Mechanisms

- Hydroquinone formation
- Hydroxylation

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